

As we approach the end of the year, we are delighted to introduce our newsletter, which highlights the outcomes of our dedicated efforts and significant advancements in our project.

Since our previous newsletter, we have continued to make significant strides in the project. Our blog section has seen remarkable expansion, offering an extensive collection of in-depth articles that explore various facets of our project.

Additionally, We are also excited to share our first YouTube video, providing a comprehensive insight into the EDGELESS project. It's a must-see for anyone intrigued by our work.

Our Latest Highlights

EDGELESS 1st Video

[Watch now](#)

Events

EDGELESS at CyberHOT 2023 Summer School

EDGELESS actively participated in the CyberHOT 2023 Summer School, held on September 29, 2023, at the NATO Maritime Interdiction Operational Training Centre (NMIOTC) in Chania, Crete, Greece.

[Read more ...](#)

1st EDGELESS Hackathon

A hackathon has been organised as part of the activities of the EDGELESS project, funded by the European Union within the Horizon Europe framework programme. This event took place at the Technical University of Munich in Garching, Germany, on September 27-28, 2023.

[Read more ...](#)

New Publications

Oakestra: A Lightweight Hierarchical Orchestration Framework for Edge Computing

Characterizing Distributed Mobile Augmented Reality Applications at the Edge

[More](#)

EDGELESS Blogs!

Maximizing efficiency and performance: SLA assessment of serverless functions in Edge environments

The arrival of the Edge and serverless computing has transformed the way people deliver and consume digital services.

[Read more ...](#)

EDGELESS Smart City Surveillance Use Case

This use case consists of a complete computer vision surveillance serverless application leveraging EDGELESS's orchestration and flexibility capabilities.

[Read more ...](#)

Event-Driven Architectures: Serverless Meets Industrial Systems

The EDGELESS project addresses major challenges and pain points to support an easier integration with existing industrial systems and to enhance the speed at which such systems can be bootstrapped.

[Read more ...](#)

[Read more articles here](#)

CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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